

Systems Versioning: A Features-Based Meta-Modeling Approach

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Abstract : Systems running these days are huge, complex and exist in many versions. Controlling these versions and tracking their changes became a very hard process as some versions are created using meaningless names or specifications. Many versions of a system are created with no clear difference between them. This leads to mismatching between a user's request and the version he gets. In this paper, we present a system versions meta-modeling approach that produces versions based on system's features. This model reduced the number of steps needed to configure a release and gave each version its unique specifications. This approach is applicable for systems that use features in its specification.

Keywords : features, meta-modeling, semantic modeling, SPL, VCS, versioning

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